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27

28 **Supplementary Methods**

29 **Taxon Sampling for UCE data**

30 We assembled UCE data from 138 species, representing 47 of 54 anuran families (87%,
31 Supplementary File S2), using published and new data. Streicher et al. (2018) sampled
32 extensively within Hyloidea (and outgroups), including data for 54 species for up to 2,214 UCEs.
33 We used these data and UCE data from 7 species from Hutter et al. (2022), who sampled broadly
34 across Anura and targeted 2,085 UCEs.

35 We obtained new data for species of Ranoidea ($n=42$) and Archaeobatrachia ($n=11$). We
36 sampled 17 of 18 ranoid families (all but Micrixalidae). Within Archaeobatrachia, we sampled
37 all families but Leiopelmatidae. We also sampled additional species ($n=17$) from several diverse
38 families in Hyloidea.

39 Finally, we used published genomes to extract UCE data from 24 species, including 7
40 frog species, various amphibian outgroups (Caudata, Gymnophiona), and more distant non-
41 amphibian outgroups. Details of taxon sampling are in Supplementary File S2.

42

43 **Details of UCE Data Collection**

44 We extracted DNA from 67 tissue samples (Supplementary File S2, Table S1) using the Qiagen
45 DNEasy Blood & Tissue Kit. DNA concentration was quantified using a Qubit DNA BR assay
46 (Life Technologies), and 1,500 ng of DNA per sample was sheared using a BioRuptor
47 (Diagenode). We used the FrogCap protocol to perform target capture for 21 of the 70 samples,
48 following methods detailed in Hutter et al. (2022). For the other 49 samples, we performed a
49 targeted UCE capture. Initially all samples were subjected to 10 cycles (30 sec on/30 sec off) to
50 achieve a target size of 400–600 bp. Fragmentation was assessed using a BioAnalyzer 2100
51 (Agilent). Several samples required an additional 8 or 16 cycles for fragmentation. We prepared
52 libraries from the fragmented DNA using the Kapa HyperPrep kit (Roche). We followed the
53 standard protocol but used Serapure beads for cleanup steps and TruSeq DNA unique dual index
54 adapters (IDT for Illumina). We used the myBaits UCE Tetrapods 5Kv1 probe set (8-reaction kit
55 size, Arbor Biosciences) for captures, following the v4.01 protocol. We pooled 6–7 libraries for
56 each capture reaction (1500 ng total input DNA) and performed hybridization for 24 hrs. Post-
57 capture PCR amplification used 12 cycles, and the post-cleanup product was eluted in 12 μ L of

58 buffer EB (10mM Tris-HCl). The eight capture products were pooled in equimolar amounts and
59 sequenced on one lane of an Illumina HiSeq4000 with 150 bp paired-end (PE) reads.

60

61 UCE Data Processing

62 We obtained UCE data from a variety of sources, including new sequence data, published whole
63 genomes, and multiple UCE target capture studies. To maintain consistency, we re-processed the
64 published sequence data using the same analysis pipeline as our newly generated data. The major
65 pipeline steps included adapter trimming and read-quality filtering, de novo assembly, and UCE
66 identification using PHYLUCE version 1.6.6 (Faircloth 2016), and filtering based on coverage.
67 The UCE sequences obtained from the new sequence data, whole genomes, and published
68 datasets were then combined and analyzed using SuperCRUNCH (Portik and Wiens 2020). We
69 describe these methods in greater detail below.

70 *UCEs from Whole-Genome Datasets.* We used published genomes to extract new UCE
71 data for 12 amphibian species (including eight frogs, three caecilians, and one salamander) and
72 nine outgroup species (Supplementary File S1). We downloaded all genomes in FASTA format
73 and converted these files to 2bit format using the faToTwoBit program of the UCSC Genome
74 Browser (Kent et al. 2002). PHYLUCE was used to align the tetrapod 5k UCE probe set (5,060
75 loci) to each 2bit genome file using LASTZ (Harris 2007). We then used PHYLUCE to extract
76 all relevant UCE sequences, retaining up to 500 base pairs of flanking sequence per side. Finally,
77 we used a script to relabel the sequences ([https://github.com/dportik/phyluce-genomes-to-](https://github.com/dportik/phyluce-genomes-to-super crunch)
78 [super crunch](https://github.com/dportik/phyluce-genomes-to-super crunch)) to ensure compatibility with SuperCRUNCH.

79 *UCEs from Target-Capture Datasets.* We obtained new sequence data for 67 samples,
80 published sequence data from the NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA) for 58 samples, and
81 previously assembled contigs for 10 species (Supplementary File S1). The SRA data included 54
82 frogs (Streicher et al. 2018) and four salamanders (Newman and Austin 2016; Denton et al.
83 2018), whereas the contig sets for 10 species came from Hutter et al. (2022). We used sratoolkit
84 and fastqdump from the SRAToolkit (v2.9.6) to obtain fastq files for the SRA samples and used
85 Trimmomatic (Bolger et al. 2014) or FASTP (Chen et al. 2018) to remove adapters and low-
86 quality reads from the fastq files (newly sequenced and SRA).

87 The Illumina sequence data were obtained using different instruments and contained
88 different read lengths (100, 150, and 300 bp PE). Consequently, they required a flexible strategy

89 for assembly. We used VelvetOptimiser (<https://github.com/tseemann/VelvetOptimiser>) to de
90 novo assemble each sample with Velvet (v.1.2.1; Zerbino and Birney 2008). Given the variation
91 in read lengths across samples, we generated assemblies using a range of hash values (55–105,
92 by increments of 10). This resulted in six Velvet assemblies per sample. We also used aTRAM2
93 (Allen et al. 2015, 2018) to perform an iterative, seeded assembly for each sample. For this
94 method, we used the UCE Tetrapods 5Kv1 probe sequences as the bait sequences, and Velvet as
95 the assembler. For each of the seven assemblies per sample (e.g., six from Velvet, one from
96 aTRAM2), we used PHYLUCe to identify contigs matching UCes. We used
97 *phyluce_assembly_match_contigs_to_probes* to align the tetrapod 5k UCE probes to each contig
98 set using LASTZ. We then ran *phyluce_assembly_get_match_counts* and
99 *phyluce_assembly_get_fastas_from_match_counts* to extract sequences for all matched UCes.

100 The published UCE data from Hutter et al. (2022) and the 18 samples with FrogCap UCE
101 data were provided as contigs assembled through the pipeline in Hutter et al. (2022). These had
102 been previously assembled using SPAdes v3.12 (Bankevich et al. 2012). For these data, we used
103 PHYLUCe to identify and extract UCE sequences as described above.

104 We performed a final filtering step for all UCE contigs. For each assembly (Velvet,
105 aTRAM2, or Spades), we used nucleotide BLAST (dc-megablast) to match the UCE contigs to
106 the tetrapod 5k UCE probe set. We removed any UCE contig that matched probes for more than
107 one UCE and removed any UCE contig that matched a probe containing a different UCE label.
108 For the Velvet and aTRAM2 assemblies, we then mapped the reads to the filtered UCE contigs
109 using BWA (Li and Durbin 2009). Picard (v.1.119; <https://broadinstitute.github.io/picard/>) was
110 used to mark and remove PCR duplicates, and coverage was estimated using the depth module of
111 Samtools (Li et al. 2009). We removed all UCE contigs with <5X coverage. Among the
112 1,205,752 starting UCE contigs, this action removed 225,009 (18.6%) low coverage contigs,
113 resulting in the retention of 980,743 contigs. This coverage filter primarily affected contigs from
114 Streicher et al. (2018), which were generated from substantially fewer reads (Illumina MiSeq)
115 relative to the other datasets.

116 For samples assembled using Velvet, our goal was to maximize the number of UCes
117 obtained. We therefore compared the number of filtered UCes obtained across the different hash
118 values and selected the assembly with the highest number. For a given sample, the selected
119 Velvet assembly and aTRAM2 assembly contained redundant UCE sequences, but each method

120 also resulted in unique UCE sequences that increased the overall yield of UCEs. We therefore
121 kept the UCE sequences from both assemblies and used SuperCRUNCH to select the best
122 sequence per UCE (see below). To investigate whether this approach produced more UCE
123 sequences than either method alone, we also analyzed the Velvet and aTRAM2 contigs
124 separately.

125 *UCE SuperCRUNCH Analysis.* We used SuperCRUNCH to create UCE-specific FASTA
126 files, and for each file to perform sequence-similarity filtering, sequence selection, alignment,
127 and trimming. To properly process local sequence data (i.e., data not downloaded directly from
128 GenBank), SuperCRUNCH requires FASTA description lines to contain a unique identifier,
129 taxon name, and locus abbreviation/description (mimicking NCBI GenBank format). We
130 relabeled the UCE sequences obtained from whole genomes and target captures to comply with
131 these criteria. All UCE sequences were combined into a single FASTA file, which contained a
132 total of 417,373 sequences. SuperCRUNCH also requires a list of taxa and locus search terms to
133 assemble marker-specific FASTA files. We obtained the taxon list from the UCE FASTA file
134 (*Fasta_Get_Taxa.py*) and used the UCE 5k search-terms file included with SuperCRUNCH. The
135 taxon list and search-terms files were used to run *Parse_Loci.py*, which produced 5,041 UCE
136 files containing at least two sequences.

137 We performed similarity filtering for each UCE sequence set using
138 *Cluster_Blast_Extract.py*. For each marker, this method clusters the sequences using CD-HIT-
139 EST (Li and Godzik 2006), designates the largest cluster as a BLAST reference database,
140 performs BLASTn searches for all sequences (including those in the reference cluster, excluding
141 self-hits), and outputs sequences that are trimmed based on their merged BLAST hit coordinates
142 (Portik and Wiens 2020). Following similarity filtering, we used *Filter_Seqs_and_Species.py* to
143 select a single representative sequence per species per UCE, taking the longest available
144 sequence if multiple sequences were present (two sequences could occur for a UCE for samples
145 assembled with Velvet and aTRAM2). During selection, we enforced a 200-base pair minimum
146 length to retain a sequence (following recommendations of Hosner et al. 2015). After the
147 selection of representative sequences, we screened the UCE markers to ensure they contained at
148 least 10 species using *Fasta_Filter_by_Min_Seqs.py*. We ensured that each UCE marker
149 contained more than just outgroup sequences.

150 Sequence alignment and trimming were performed following recommendations for UCEs
151 by Portik and Wiens (2021). We used MAFFT v7.475 (Katoh et al. 2002, 2005; Katoh and
152 Standley 2013) with the automatic algorithm selection option and performed trimming with
153 trimAl (Capella-Gutiérrez et al. 2009) using a gap-threshold value of 0.2. This trimming
154 threshold removes columns containing gaps for more than 80% of the sequences present.
155 Sequences were relabeled prior to trimming using *Fasta_Relabel_Seqs.py*, such that they only
156 included species names (vs. full description lines). Finally, we concatenated the trimmed UCE
157 alignments using *Concatenation.py*. We refer to this as the UCE dataset.

158

159 Assembling UCE Contigs

160 To maximize the overall yield of sequences, we used a strategy that involved combining two
161 methods to assemble UCE contigs. Using both methods produced a combined total of 313,361
162 UCE sequences (185,517 from Velvet, 127,844 from aTRAM2). However, this combined set
163 likely contained many redundant sequences (e.g., the same UCE locus was assembled for a
164 species by both methods). To explore this idea, we used SuperCRUNCH to analyze each contig
165 set separately and to analyze the combined contig set. The total number of sequences obtained by
166 analyzing the aTRAM2 dataset alone was 85,895, and the analysis of the Velvet dataset alone
167 produced only 179,088 total sequences. The combined analysis resulted in 209,791 total UCE
168 sequences, with 125,743 resulting from Velvet assemblies and 84,048 resulting from aTRAM2.
169 These results indicate that performing assembly with multiple methods and selecting sequences
170 with SuperCRUNCH improved the overall yield of UCEs by ~30,000 sequences (relative to the
171 Velvet results), with an average increase of ~200 sequences per sample.

172

173 Details of Supermatrix Construction

174 We generated a supermatrix to allow us to include as many anuran genera as possible. We
175 identified 22 molecular markers that have been widely used in anuran phylogenetics (e.g., Pyron
176 and Wiens 2011; Jetz and Pyron 2018). These included 15 nuclear genes (*BDNF*, *BMP2*, *CMYC*,
177 *CXCR4*, *H3A*, *NCX1*, *NT3*, *POMC*, *RAG1*, *RAG2*, *RHO*, *SIA*, *SLC8A3*, *TNS3*, *TYR*) and seven
178 mitochondrial (mt) genes (*12S*, *16S*, *COI*, *CYTB*, *ND1*, *ND2*, *ND4*). For both *RAG1* and *COI*,
179 multiple primer designs have led to two non-overlapping regions being sequenced, and we

180 therefore treated each of these markers as having two distinct regions. We refer to these 22 genes
181 as the “legacy” markers since they have been widely used in previous phylogenetic studies.

182 In addition to these traditional GenBank markers, we also included two sets of nuclear
183 markers that were available for smaller numbers of taxa. The first set included 92 markers
184 sequenced by Feng et al. (2017) and Tu et al. (2018). These were available for a total of 156 frog
185 species. These are a subset of the PCR-based nuclear protein-coding loci (NPCL) described in
186 Shen et al. (2013). The second set included 230 taxa with 220 nuclear markers sequenced by
187 Hime et al. (2021). These are conserved nuclear exon sequences obtained through anchored-
188 hybrid enrichment (AHE; Lemmon et al. 2012). We determined that 26 markers were shared
189 between these two datasets, with no taxonomic overlap. We ultimately constructed alignments
190 for these shared markers using a combination of the AHE and NPCL sequences, but for
191 categorization we considered these to be NPCL markers.

192 In total, we included 286 non-UCE markers. All sequences for the legacy and NPCL
193 markers were available on GenBank. To obtain them, we downloaded all available sequences for
194 Anura from NCBI on November 17, 2020. We obtained AHE sequences by downloading
195 alignment files from the supplemental materials provided in Hime et al. (2021). To make the
196 AHE data compatible with SuperCRUNCH, we stripped the alignments (i.e., removed all gaps),
197 updated the taxon labels to be compatible with the taxonomy of AmphibiaWeb, assigned each
198 sequence a unique identifier (e.g., “accession” number), and added gene-description terms. We
199 downloaded the AmphibiaWeb taxonomy on November 17, 2020 and created a taxon list
200 containing all recognized anuran species at that time ($n=7,266$). We then generated a marker
201 search-terms file that included all 314 of these markers.

202 We created marker-specific FASTA files in SuperCRUNCH using *Parse_Loci.py*. We
203 then performed sequence-similarity filtering steps with *Cluster_Blast_Extract.py* for most
204 markers to ensure the same target regions were obtained for alignment. This method: (i) creates
205 sequence clusters using CD-HIT-EST (Li and Godzik 2006) at the 80% sequence identity
206 threshold, (ii) performs BLASTn searches (dc-megablast) for all sequences using the largest
207 sequence cluster as the reference database, and (iii) outputs sequences that are trimmed based on
208 their merged BLAST hit coordinates (Portik and Wiens 2020). We used
209 *Reference_Blast_Extract.py* to perform sequence-similarity filtering for markers with complex
210 records (those containing the target region plus non-target sequence), which included all mtDNA

211 markers and both regions of *RAG1*. This method differs from *Cluster_Blast_Extract.py* only by
212 requiring a user-supplied set of reference sequences to use as the BLAST reference database (vs.
213 a cluster generated from the input sequences). For reference sequences, we used the vertebrate
214 RAG1 and the anuran mtDNA reference sets available from SuperCRUNCH
215 (<https://github.com/dportik/SuperCRUNCH/tree/master/data/reference-sequence-sets>). We used
216 *Filter_Seqs_and_Species.py* to select one sequence per species per gene (-s oneseq) based on the
217 longest available sequence (-f length), with a minimum sequence length requirement of 300 bp (-
218 m 300). For protein-coding markers, we pre-processed all sequences using
219 *Coding_Translation_Tests.py*, which identifies the correct reading frame of sequences, adjusts
220 them to the first codon position, and ensures completion of the final codon. We then used the
221 MACSE v2 translation aligner (Ranwez et al. 2018), which can align coding sequences with
222 respect to their translation while accounting for multiple frameshifts or stop codons. For all other
223 markers we used MAFFT (Kato et al. 2002, 2005; Kato and Standley 2013) with the automatic
224 alignment algorithm selection option.

225 We counted the number of markers with representation for each species across the
226 different sets of markers (legacy, NPCL, AHE, and UCE). For each marker set, we selected the
227 species with the greatest amount of data to represent a given genus. Thus, each genus is
228 represented by one terminal taxon, but does not necessarily have data for the same species for
229 each marker (Supplementary File S3). Accession numbers for all GenBank sequences selected
230 (legacy and NPCL markers) are provided in Supplementary File S4. We obtained data for one or
231 more of the selected markers for 441 of 456 frog described genera (96.7%; AmphibiaWeb 2021).

232 We generated two major concatenated data matrices. One contained all markers except
233 the UCE markers. We refer to this as the supermatrix dataset. The other combined this
234 supermatrix with the UCE data. We refer to this combined UCE-supermatrix dataset as the
235 gigamatrix. These concatenated matrices were generated in SuperCRUNCH, after the selected
236 sequences for each marker were relabeled with genus names. The basic properties of the
237 different datasets are given in Tables 2 and 3 and in Supplementary File S2, Fig. S1. All
238 individual alignments and the gigamatrix (with partition files) are provided on an Open Science
239 Framework project page: <https://osf.io/fzw3x/>.

240

241 **Phylogenetic Analyses**

242 The UCE data were analyzed using both concatenated maximum likelihood (ML) and gene-tree
243 summary methods. For the combined supermatrix and gigamatrix datasets, we only performed
244 concatenated ML analyses given that many genera had data for only a few genes. We chose
245 RAxML for all ML analyses because RAxML was found to obtain better results than IQ-TREE
246 (Nguyen et al. 2015) for phylogenomic datasets containing >200 taxa (Zhou et al. 2018).

247 For the UCE data, we used RAxML v8.2 (Stamatakis 2014) on the Cyberinfrastructure
248 for Phylogenetic Research (CIPRES) Science Gateway (Miller et al. 2010). We performed 50
249 alternate runs on distinct starting trees to find the best-scoring ML tree and conducted 100 rapid
250 bootstrap analyses. We used the standard GTR+CAT model (general-time-reversible model with
251 the CAT approximation of the gamma distribution of rates among sites, which is considered the
252 optimal model in RAxML for very large datasets; Stamatakis 2006). We did not partition the
253 UCE data because vertebrate UCE loci are often not protein-coding, and partition schemes are
254 therefore unresolved (but see Tagliacollo and Lanfear 2018). Furthermore, as we describe below,
255 using a large number of partitions was simply not practical for these datasets. We also found
256 little difference between trees from partitioned and unpartitioned analyses.

257 We conducted species-tree analyses of the UCE data using a gene-tree summary method,
258 ASTRAL-III (Mirarab et al. 2014; Mirarab and Warnow 2015; Zhang et al. 2017). A gene tree
259 was constructed for each UCE using RAxML v8.2. Given the large number of UCEs, we used
260 the relatively fast GTR+CAT model, with 10 replicate searches per gene. The complete set of
261 gene trees was used to infer a species tree using ASTRAL-III. Branch support was assessed
262 using local posterior probabilities (LPP), which are computed from gene-tree quartet frequencies
263 (Sayyari and Mirarab 2016). We also visualized the level of congruence among gene trees on
264 each branch of the UCE species-tree. Specifically, we used ASTRAL-III version 5.7.8 to output
265 quartet support values on the species tree. These values represent the percentage of gene tree
266 quartets that agree with each node in the species tree (Sayyari and Mirarab 2016). The results
267 generally show that congruence between genes is greater on longer branches (i.e., in the
268 concatenated ML tree), as expected from theory and previous studies (e.g., Wiens et al. 2008).

269 We used PartitionFinder2 (Lanfear et al. 2016) to identify the best partitioning scheme
270 for our supermatrix and gigamatrix datasets. It was not possible to run PartitionFinder2 on the
271 gigamatrix (combined UCE+supermatrix), even with greatly reduced taxon sampling and when

272 treating the UCEs as a single concatenated locus. Therefore, we analyzed the supermatrix dataset
273 and extended these results to the gigamatrix, treating the UCEs as a single partition.

274 We performed two partitioning analyses. For the first analysis, the input partitions
275 consisted of separate partitions for each codon position in each gene (with a single partition for
276 non-protein coding genes, like 12S and 16S). For the second analysis, there was a single partition
277 per gene. The best-fit partitioning schemes for these analyses had 916 and 225 partitions,
278 respectively (Supplementary File S6). The GTR+gamma model was selected as the best RAxML
279 model for most partitions (>90%) recovered in both analyses. Given that only one model type
280 can be specified across each partition in RAxML, we selected GTR+gamma to represent all
281 partitions. Running each of these partitioned datasets was computationally intractable on
282 CIPRES. Specifically, the analyses failed in the first few minutes.

283 We therefore used a simpler partitioning scheme for the gigamatrix that contained a total
284 of eight partitions: a partition for each of the three codon positions in the nuclear protein-coding
285 genes, a partition for each of the three codon position in the mitochondrial protein-coding genes,
286 a single partition for mitochondrial ribosomal RNA (including 12S and 16S), and one partition
287 consisting of the UCEs (Supplementary File S6). We used seven partitions for the supermatrix
288 (identical but with the exclusion of the UCEs). We then performed partitioned analyses of the
289 supermatrix and gigamatrix datasets.

290 Given the large size of the gigamatrix we performed an initial investigation of the
291 computational resources required. We first ran the dataset without partitions, using the
292 GTR+CAT model with 10 replicate searches for the optimal tree.

293 For the gigamatrix, we conducted 10 alternate runs on distinct starting trees to find the
294 best-scoring ML tree. To complete the analysis within CIPRES run-time allotments, we
295 performed two separate analyses involving 5 alternate runs on distinct starting trees, with a final
296 branch-length optimization on the best tree found in each analysis. Due to limitations in
297 computational resources, our search for the best tree was not extensive. To address this potential
298 shortcoming, we calculated the pairwise distance of Robinson and Foulds (1981) for the 10
299 optimized trees to determine their overall topological similarity. We then conducted four
300 separate bootstrapping analyses of 25 bootstraps (to allow completion within CIPRES run-time
301 allotments). These replicates were then combined manually to obtain a total of 100 rapid
302 bootstrap replicates.

303 In addition to bootstrap analyses, for the gigamatrix tree we also calculated gene
304 concordance factors (gCF) and site concordance factors (sCF) using IQ-TREE2 (Nguyen et al.
305 2015; Minh et al. 2020). The gCF is based on the proportion of loci that are consistent with a
306 particular branch among the loci that are decisive for that branch (i.e., they could contain that
307 branch). By contrast, the sCF is the average proportion of sites that are decisive for a given
308 branch that are concordant with that branch. The latter is calculated at the per-site level, rather
309 than whole-alignment level (i.e., it is performed with quartet approaches). We also included a
310 summary of the number of decisive genes and sites for each branch (gN and sN; Minh et al.
311 2020). This was especially helpful for visualizing the data associated with each branch, given the
312 variation in gene sampling among terminal taxa.

313 We analyzed the supermatrix in a similar fashion, using a partitioned analysis and the
314 GTR+gamma model assigned to all seven partitions (see above). However, use of the
315 GTR+gamma model required only ~1 Gb memory for the supermatrix. Therefore, we were able
316 to conduct a more thorough search (50 alternate runs on distinct starting trees) to look for the
317 best-scoring ML tree.

318 For the gigamatrix dataset (combined UCE+supermatrix), we were interested in
319 identifying potential rogue taxa. These are taxa that are highly unstable in their phylogenetic
320 placement and can reduce branch support in parts of the tree because of their instability. We used
321 RogueNaRok (Aberer et al. 2013) to perform these analyses, using the best-scoring ML tree and
322 bootstrap trees as inputs. The set of rogue taxa ($n=29$) was removed from the gigamatrix, and we
323 ran an additional concatenated ML analysis with RAxML with 100 rapid bootstraps.

324

325 Time-calibrated Phylogeny

326 We estimated divergence times for the gigamatrix trees. We used penalized likelihood
327 implemented with treePL (Sanderson, 2001; Smith and O'Meara, 2012). This is a standard
328 approach for estimating divergence times for large trees. It is particularly advantageous here in
329 that it used the maximum-likelihood branch lengths already calculated, rather than re-estimating
330 these across thousands of loci. We removed non-amphibian outgroups prior to conducting
331 divergence-time estimation. We conducted a thorough analysis in treePL during two
332 optimization phases, one for search settings and one for smoothing parameter identification. The
333 "thorough" setting ensures the analysis continue to iterate until convergence of log likelihoods is

334 observed. We tested the following standard smoothing values in treePL: 0.1, 1, 10, 100, 1,000,
335 and 10,000. We conducted analyses on both the full gigamatrix tree and on the tree with the 29
336 rogue taxa excluded.

337 We used 16 fossil calibration points in the dating analyses. To find fossil calibration
338 points we reviewed those used in recent large-scale time-calibrated phylogenies of amphibians
339 (Feng et al. 2017; Jetz and Pyron 2018; Hime et al. 2021) and included other recent works on
340 fossil frogs (see below). We used the geological time scale version 5.0 (Walker et al. 2018).
341 Below, we list the fossil calibration points used.

342 The calibration points listed below were minimum ages with a single exception: we used
343 a maximum value for Batrachia of 251.2 Mya, following Benton et al. (2015). This follows from
344 the absence of crown lissamphibians from the Permian fossil record (Benton et al. 2015;
345 Cannatella 2015).

346

347 1) Batrachia crown group (crown-group of frogs and salamanders). Feng et al. (2017) used a
348 minimum date of 247.2 Mya for *Triadobatrachus massinoti*, following Cannatella (2015). This is
349 a stem anuran from the Early Triassic (Carroll 1988; Rage and Roček 1989). Jetz and Pyron
350 (2018) used 245 Mya. The minimum age for the beginning of the Early Triassic is 247.2 Mya.

351 Crown-group age of Batrachia: minimum=247.2 Mya; maximum=251.2 Mya

352

353 2) Alytoidea crown group (crown-group of Alytidae+Bombinatoridae). Feng et al. (2017) used
354 *Iberobatrachus angelae* to set a minimum age of 125 Mya for the alytoid crown group. The
355 phylogenetic analysis by Báez (2013) placed this taxon as the sister to *Discoglossus*, but did not
356 show Alytidae as monophyletic (but instead as paraphyletic with respect to Bombinatoridae). We
357 conservatively used this taxon to set the minimum age for the alytoid crown group. This taxon is
358 from the Late Barremian. According to Walker et al. (2018) the minimum age for the Late
359 Barremian is 125.0 Mya.

360 Crown-group age of Alytoidea: minimum=125.0 Mya

361

362 3) Alytidae. Fossils of the genus *Latonia* (Roček and Rage 2000) have been shown to be within
363 crown-group Discoglossidae (Yuan et al. 2000) and are at least 23.0 Mya (Late Oligocene). In

364 the tree estimated here, *Latonia* and *Discoglossus* are sister taxa, and so we used these fossils to
365 set the minimum age of the split between them.

366 Crown-group age of *Latonia* + *Discoglossus*: minimum=23.0 Mya.

367

368 4) Pipoidea crown group (crown-group of Pipidae+Rhinophryniidae). Feng et al. (2017) used the
369 fossil *Rhadinosteus parvus* to set a minimum age for Papanura (crown group of Pipoidea +
370 Pelobatoidea + Neobatrachia) at 148.1 Mya, following Cannatella (2015). The analysis by Báez
371 (2013) showed that *Rhadinosteus parvus* is more closely related to *Rhinophrynus* than
372 *Pipa*+*Xenopus*. Therefore, we used this taxon to set the minimum age of Pipoidea
373 (Rhinophryniidae+Pipidae) and not Papanura (although equal-weights parsimony analyses by
374 Gómez (2016) placed *Rhadinosteus* in a polytomy with other pipoids). *Rhadinosteus parvus* is
375 from the Late Jurassic (Tithonian), and Cannatella (2015) reviewed evidence suggesting that the
376 appropriate minimum age is 148.1 Mya (based on the age of the Brush Bush Formation where
377 the taxon was found). Note that this is older than the minimum age of 127.2 Mya set for Pipoidea
378 by Feng et al. (2017), using *Neusibatrachus wilferti* or *Cordicephalus* (125 Mya) used by Jetz
379 and Pyron (2018).

380 Crown-group age of Pipoidea: minimum=148.1 Mya

381

382 5) Pipidae crown group. Feng et al. (2017) used the pipid fossil *Pachycentrata taqueti* to set a
383 minimum age of 83.6 Mya for this family, following Cannatella (2015). Cannatella (2015) noted
384 that the minimum age of the formation in which this fossil was found is 83.6 Mya, based on the
385 age of the “In Beceten” Formation from the late Coniacian-Santonian (Upper Cretaceous). The
386 minimum age of the Santonian is 83.6 Mya (Walker et al. 2018). Cannatella (2015) used a
387 phylogenetic analysis to show that this taxon is within the crown-group of Pipidae.

388 Crown-group age of Pipidae: minimum=83.6 Mya

389

390 6) Scaphiopodidae crown group. We used a minimum age of 50.3 Mya, given a fossil
391 scaphiopodid (*Scaphiopus guthriei*) from the Wind River formation (lower Eocene Wasatchian
392 50.3—55.4 Mya) that is more closely related to *Scaphiopus* than to *Spea* (Gao and Chen 2017).
393 We assigned this taxon to the crown-group of Scaphiopodidae, which contains only two living
394 genera (*Scaphiopus*, *Spea*).

395 Crown-group age of Scaphiropodidae: minimum=50.3 Mya

396

397 7) Clade of Pelobatidae and Megophryidae (crown group). The analysis of Chen et al. (2016)
398 found *Gobiates spinari* nested within a clade containing Megophryidae + Pelobatidae. We used
399 this taxon as a minimum calibration point for this clade. *Gobiates spinari* is from the Coniacian
400 (Upper Cretaceous) of Uzbekistan (Roček 2008). According to Walker et al. (2018) the
401 minimum age for the Coniacian is 86.3 Mya. Feng et al. (2017) used *Elkobatrachus brocki* with
402 a minimum age of 46.1 Mya to date the crown group of Pelobatoidea, and the fossil pelodytid
403 frog *Miopelodytes gilmorei* (minimum age of 38.9 Mya) following Henrici and Haynes (2006),
404 to date the clade of Pelodytidae + Pelobatidae + Megophryidae. We did not use these two
405 calibration points because the older age of *Gobiates spinari* for the younger clade Pelobatidae +
406 Megophryidae makes them redundant.

407 Crown-group age of Pelobatidae+Megophryidae: minimum=86.3 Mya

408

409 8) Calyptocephalellidae (crown group). We used a minimum age of 61.7 Mya, given fossil
410 *Calyptocephalella* (formerly *Caudiverbera*) from the Early Paleocene (65.5–61.7 Mya; Báez
411 2000). Feng et al. (2017) used the fossil *Calyptocephalella pichileufensis* to set a minimum age
412 of 47.5 Mya for the Myobatrachoidea (Myobatrachidae + Calyptocephalellidae). However, given
413 the taxon sampling here, this fossil should instead set the minimum age for the split between the
414 two genera of Calyptocephalellidae (*Calyptocephalella* and *Telmatobufo*). Furthermore, we used
415 the older fossil calibration point for this genus.

416 Crown-group age of Calyptocephalellidae: minimum=61.7 Mya.

417

418 9) Myobatrachidae (crown group). We used a minimum age of 54.6 Mya, given fossils assigned
419 to the extant myobatrachid genus *Lechriodus* (Sanchiz 1998; Evans et al. 2008). We assumed
420 that the precise phylogenetic placement of this taxon was not known, and so we merely assigned
421 it to the Myobatrachidae crown group.

422 Crown-group age of Myobatrachidae: minimum=54.6 Mya

423

424 10) Hylidae: Pelodryadinae stem group. Pelodryadine fossils are present from the late Oligocene
425 of Australia (23.0–28.4 Mya; Sanchiz 1998). Therefore, we set the minimum age of the split
426 between Pelodryadinae and its sister group (Phyllomedusinae) to be at least 23.0 Mya.

427 Stem-group age of Pelodryadinae: minimum=23.0 Mya

428

429 11) Hylidae: crown-group age of *Acris* + *Pseudacris*. Given the fossil taxon *Acris barbouri* from
430 the Miocene (Hemingfordian: 16.3–20.6 Mya) of Florida (Holman, 2003; Marjanovic and
431 Laurin, 2007), we set a minimum age of 16.3 Mya on the split between the genera *Acris* and
432 *Pseudacris*.

433 Crown-group age of *Acris* + *Pseudacris*: minimum=16.3 Mya

434

435 12) Eleutherodactylidae: Eleutherodactylinae crown group. For the age of this clade, we used the
436 minimum age in the Oligocene of the San Sebastian Formation in Puerto Rico (~29.5 Mya) from
437 which a fossil referred to as *Eleutherodactylus* was described by Blackburn et al. (2020). Poinar
438 and Cannatella (1987) described an amber fossil of *Eleutherodactylus* from the La Toca
439 formation (Dominican Republic) as being from the Eocene, but these deposits have been more
440 recently interpreted as Miocene in age. The content of *Eleutherodactylus* has changed
441 considerably over time, but *Eleutherodactylus* (sensu stricto) is the only genus of terraranans that
442 currently occurs on Puerto Rico (and other islands of the Greater Antilles). Therefore, we
443 assigned this fossil to the genus *Eleutherodactylus* and used it as a minimum age constraint on
444 the crown-group age of the subfamily (which also contains the mainland genus *Diasporus*).

445 Crown-group age of Eleutherodactylinae (*Diasporus*+*Eleutherodactylus*):

446 minimum=29.5 Mya

447

448 13) Crown Bufonidae. We used a minimum age of 56.0 Mya, given fossils of putative *Bufo*
449 (sensu lato) from the late Paleocene (56.0–59.2 Mya; Báez 2000; Báez and Nicoli 2004; Walker
450 et al. 2018). We considered these fossils to be within the crown group of Bufonidae, given that
451 they were considered to be “unquestionable” remains of *Bufo*, sensu lato (Báez and Nicoli 2004),
452 which represents a subclade within the bufonid crown group.

453 Crown age of Bufonidae: minimum=56.0 Mya

454

455 14) Stem *Rhinella*. Báez and Nicoli (2004) identified bufonid fossils that they considered to be
456 closely related to extant *Rhinella arenarum*, from the late Oligocene (specifically 29.4–25.5
457 Mya). We used these fossils to set the minimum age for the split between *Rhinella* and its sister
458 group. In the gigamatrix tree, *Rhinella* is sister group to a large clade including most bufonid
459 genera that were formerly within *Bufo* (e.g., *Anaxyrus*, *Incillius*, *Duttaphrynus*) and their close
460 relatives (e.g., *Nectophrynoides*, *Pedostibes*).

461 Stem age of *Rhinella*: minimum=25.5 Mya

462

463 15) Stem Ptychadenidae. Following Feng et al. (2017), we constrained the minimum age of the
464 node uniting Ptychadenidae and Phrynobatrachidae based on a fossil of Ptychadenidae that was
465 well-dated to 24.5–25.5 Mya (Blackburn et al. 2015). We used a date of 24.5 Mya to constrain
466 the minimum age of the split between Ptychadenidae and its putative sister group in our tree,
467 Phrynobatrachidae.

468 Crown age of Ptychadenidae+Phrynobatrachidae: minimum=24.5 Mya.

469

470 16) Crown Pyxicephalidae. We set a minimum age for the crown group of Pyxicephalidae based
471 on the fossil taxon *Thaumastosaurus* (Lemierre et al. 2021). The oldest remains of this genus are
472 from the late middle Eocene of Europe, dated to ~39.5 Mya (Lemierre et al. 2021). Lemierre et
473 al. (2021) considered this taxon to belong to the subfamily Pyxicephalinae, based on their
474 phylogenetic analyses (e.g., their Fig. 15). However, to be conservative we used it to date the
475 crown-group age of the family.

476 Crown age of Pyxicephalidae: minimum=39.5 Mya

477

478 **Supplementary Results**

479 **Monophyly of Subfamilies**

480 The gigamatrix tree (Fig. 3) also supported the monophyly of most subfamilies in which two or
481 more genera were sampled. Following the taxonomy of AmphibiaWeb (2020; November), these
482 subfamilies included those in: Alytidae (Discoglossinae), Megophryidae (Leptobrachiinae,
483 Megophryinae), Microhylidae (Otophryninae, Gastrophryninae, Scaphiophryninae, Cophylinae,
484 Microhylinae, Asterophryninae), Pyxicephalidae (Pyxicephalinae, Cacosterninae),
485 Ceratobatrachidae (Ceratobatrachinae), Dicroglossidae (Occidozyginae, Dicroglossinae),
486 Mantellidae (Laliostominae), Rhacophoridae (Rhacophorinae), Myobatrachidae
487 (Limnodynastinae, Myobatrachinae), Hylidae (Pelodyadinae, Phyllomedusinae, Hylinae),
488 Dendrobatidae (Hyloxalinae, Aromobatinae, Colostethinae), Eleutherodactylidae
489 (Phyzelaphryninae, Eleutherodactylinae), Strabomantidae (Holoadeninae), Centrolenidae
490 (Hyalinobatrachinae, Centroleninae), and Leptodactylidae (Paratelmatobiinae, Leptodactylinae).
491 These results suggest that highly incomplete taxa were also correctly placed in clades within
492 families, and not merely placed in the correct families.

493 We found four non-monophyletic subfamilies in the gigamatrix tree (Fig. 3). In
494 Mantellidae, we did not support monophyly of Mantellinae, given the weakly supported
495 placement of the mantelline *Tsingymantis* with Laliostominae. *Tsingymantis* is represented by 6
496 markers here and is 99.88% incomplete. In Dendrobatidae we supported monophyly of
497 Aromobatinae, Colostethinae, and Hyloxalinae, but not Dendrobatinae. Non-monophyly of
498 Dendrobatinae was not related to a single misplaced taxon: instead a strongly supported clade of
499 *Excidobates*, *Andinobates*, and *Ranitomeya* was weakly placed with Hyloxalinae and not with
500 other dendrobatine genera (but note that Dendrobatinae is monophyletic in the supermatrix tree).
501 In Leptodactylidae, we did not support monophyly of Leiuperinae, given that *Pseudopaludicola*
502 is weakly placed with Paratelmatobiinae. *Pseudopaludicola* is represented by 12 markers and is
503 99.76% incomplete. In Strabomantidae, Pristimantinae is non-monophyletic given the placement
504 of *Tachiramantis* with Craugastoridae. *Tachiramantis* is represented by 4 markers and is 99.89%
505 incomplete. Importantly, in the supermatrix tree, *Tsingymantis* does not group with other
506 mantellines, *Pseudopaludicola* is placed with Paratelmatobiinae, and *Tachiramantis* is placed
507 with Craugastoridae. Therefore, non-monophyly of Mantellinae, Leiuperinae, and Pristimantinae
508 cannot be attributed to extensive missing data arising from the assembly of the gigamatrix.

509 Furthermore, these genera are not especially incomplete (i.e., 49 genera have fewer than 6
510 markers, with 12 genera having only 1 or 2 markers).

511

512 **Analysis of Branch Lengths**

513 There was also considerable heterogeneity in branch lengths among the terminal taxa in this tree
514 (Fig. 3). We found a significant positive correlation between terminal branch lengths and missing
515 data among these terminal taxa ($\tau=0.27$, $P<0.0001$; using non-parametric Kendall correlation
516 in R; data in Supplementary File S3). Considering only taxa with a predominance of nuclear
517 markers (UCE, AHE, and/or NPCL, not those with legacy-data only), the mean terminal branch
518 length among the 234 taxa was 0.0370 substitutions/site. Among these taxa, there was a weak
519 negative correlation, such that taxa with more missing data had shorter branch lengths ($\tau=-$
520 0.09 , $P=0.0417$). The percentage of missing data for these taxa ranged from 40.7% to 96.7%.
521 Considering only species that had legacy data alone (i.e., with more equivalent numbers of
522 mitochondrial and nuclear markers), the mean terminal branch length among the 207 taxa was
523 0.0570. Among these legacy-only taxa, there was a significant positive, correlation between
524 missing data and branch lengths ($\tau=0.16$, $P=0.0007$). Yet, the percentage of missing data
525 among these taxa ranged only from 97.19% to 99.98%. We suggest that these patterns are
526 explained (at least in part) by longer branch lengths associated with faster evolutionary rates in
527 the mitochondrial markers, which predominate among the highly incomplete legacy-only taxa.
528 For example, those taxa with only 1 or 2 markers in total had only mitochondrial markers and
529 each had >99.9% missing data. Thus, the heterogeneity in branch lengths seems to be related to
530 heterogeneity in the type of data present, not the amount of missing data alone.

531

532 **Comparison To Other Recent Studies**

533 Here, we compare our main trees to those in other recent studies. Specifically, we compare our
534 concatenated UCE-only tree (Fig. 2) and combined UCE-supermatrix (gigamatrix) tree to three
535 other recent estimates: two based on phylogenomic datasets (Feng et al. 2017; Hime et al. 2021)
536 and the supermatrix study of Jetz and Pyron (2018). For brevity, we focus primarily on
537 relationships among families and other higher-level relationships. Furthermore, the
538 phylogenomic studies have limited sampling within families.

539 We first compare the overall congruence of our tree with these trees quantitatively, then
540 address specific clades. Specifically, we compared the number of nodes shared between each of
541 these trees and our gigamatrix tree (Fig. 3), for relationships among families. Some families were
542 missing in the tree of Hime et al. (2021) and the phylogenomic tree of Feng et al. (2017; their
543 Fig. 1). We excluded from these comparisons those nodes in the gigamatrix tree in which
544 directly relevant families were absent in the other trees (e.g., a clade consisting of families A+B
545 in our tree when B is absent in the other tree), but we included nodes that were potentially
546 congruent (e.g., a clade consisting of (A(B,C)) in our tree when B is absent in the other tree). For
547 the supermatrix tree of Jetz and Pyron (2018), 33 of 53 nodes were concordant (62.3%). For
548 Feng et al. (2017), this depended on the tree used. For their tree including all families (their Fig.
549 2), 35 of 53 nodes were concordant (66.0%). Much of the discordance involved the placement of
550 Cycloramphidae, Micrixalidae, and Ranixalidae, which lacked full phylogenomic data.
551 Considering their smaller, strictly phylogenomic dataset, six nodes were not comparable due to
552 missing taxa, and 43 of 47 were concordant (91.5%). For the tree of Hime et al. (2021), four
553 nodes were not comparable, and 44 of 49 were concordant (89.8%). Using a Chi-squared test in
554 R (which does not assume a normal distribution), there was a significantly higher proportion of
555 nodes shared between the gigamatrix tree and these phylogenomic trees than between the
556 gigamatrix tree and the supermatrix tree of Jetz and Pyron (2018): supermatrix vs. Hime et al.
557 (2021), $P=0.0012$; supermatrix vs. Feng et al. (2017; Fig. 1), $P=0.0006$. Overall, we found that
558 higher-level relationships in the gigamatrix tree were most concordant with those from other,
559 strictly phylogenomic datasets (e.g., Feng et al. 2017 [Fig. 1]; Hime et al. 2021), and not from
560 supermatrix datasets (e.g., Jetz and Pyron 2018). This result parallels the comparison of our own
561 gigamatrix, supermatrix, and phylogenomic trees.

562 Here, we describe the specific areas of congruence and discordance with these three
563 previous higher-level studies. Our results agree with previous studies regarding the major clades
564 of frogs. All recent studies agree on the relationships among Leiopelmatoidea
565 (Ascaphidae+Leiopelmatidae), Discoglossoidea (Alytidae, Bombinatoridae), Pipoidea
566 (Rhinophrynidae, Pipidae), Pelobatoidea (Scaphiropodidae, (Pelodytidae, (Pelobatidae,
567 Megophryidae))), and Neobatrachia. Our gigamatrix tree agrees with other recent studies in that
568 Heleophryinidae is sister to all other neobatrachians (although we lacked UCE data for

569 Heleophrynidae) and that the clade Sooglossidae+Nasikabatrachidae is sister to Ranoidea (but
570 we lacked UCE data for both families).

571 Our UCE and gigamatrix trees place Microhylidae as sister to all other Ranoidea (Figs. 2,
572 3A). This result is supported by other recent studies (Feng et al. 2017; Hime et al. 2021), except
573 for Jetz and Pyron (2018), who placed Microhylidae as sister to Afrobatrachia instead. Within
574 Afrobatrachia, our results and other recent studies agree on the relationships: ((Hemisotidae,
575 Brevicipitidae), (Hyperoliidae, Arthroleptidae)).

576 Relationships within Natatanura (all other ranoids) show considerable discordance,
577 however. Our UCE data alone place the African family Pyxicephalidae as sister to all other
578 Natatanura, including a clade of mostly African families ((Conrauidae, Petropedetidae),
579 (Odontobatrachidae, (Ptychadenidae, Phrynobatrachidae))) and a clade of mostly Asian families:
580 ((Ranixalidae, Ceratobatrachidae), ((Dicroglossidae, (Ranidae, (Mantellidae, Rhacophoridae)))).
581 These relationships are generally strongly supported (Fig. 2). The gigamatrix (combined UCE-
582 supermatrix) tree supports somewhat different relationships, which are generally weakly
583 supported (Fig. 3B). The South Asian family Micrixalidae (absent in the UCE dataset) is sister to
584 all other Natatanura, and the African families do not form a monophyletic group. The trees of
585 Feng et al. (2017) and Hime et al. (2021) both support a clade of primarily African families:
586 ((Odontobatrachidae, (Ptychadenidae, Phrynobatrachidae)), (Pyxicephalidae, (Conrauidae,
587 Petropedetidae))). All these trees (including the gigamatrix tree) agree that Conrauidae and
588 Petropedetidae are sister taxa and that Odontobatrachidae is the sister group to the clade of
589 Ptychadenidae and Phrynobatrachidae. The tree of Jetz and Pyron (2018) is more discordant: it
590 also suggests that African families form a paraphyletic group with respect to the primarily Asian
591 families, but the overall ranoid relationships are quite different.

592 Among the primarily Asian families in Natatanura, the relationships found in the UCE-
593 only and gigamatrix trees (Figs. 2, 3B) are generally concordant with those of Hime et al. (2021)
594 and the phylogenomic tree of Feng et al. (2017; their Fig. 1). The gigamatrix tree shows:
595 ((Ceratobatrachidae, (Nyctibatrachidae, Ranixalidae)), ((Dicroglossidae, (Ranidae, (Mantellidae,
596 Rhacophoridae)))). However, our UCE-only tree lacked data for Nyctibatrachidae (Fig. 2), Hime
597 et al. (2021) lacked data for Ranixalidae, and Feng et al. (2017; Fig. 1) lacked data for both. Jetz
598 and Pyron (2018) supported somewhat different relationships: ((Nyctibatrachidae,
599 Ceratobatrachidae), (((Ranixalidae, Dicroglossidae), (Ranidae, (Mantellidae, Rhacophoridae)))).

600 Furthermore, the concatenated tree of Feng et al. (2017; their Fig. 2) supported quite different
601 relationships, and placed Nyctibatrachidae as the sister group to Ranidae, and placed
602 Micrixalidae + Ranixalidae as the sister group to Mantellidae + Rhacophoridae.

603 Most studies agree that Myobatrachidae and Calyptocephalellidae form a clade that is the
604 sister group to Hyloidea, including our gigamatrix tree (Fig. 3C) and the analyses of Feng et al.
605 (2017), Jetz and Pyron (2018), and Hime et al. (2021). Surprisingly, our analysis of UCE data
606 alone suggest that this grouping is paraphyletic with respect to Hyloidea (Fig. 2).

607 Overall, hyloid relationships (Figs. 2, 3C) were broadly similar between our results and
608 those of Feng et al. (2017; Fig. 1) and Hime et al. (2021). These analyses agree that
609 Rhinodermatidae is sister to all other Hyloidea, that a clade of southern South American frogs
610 (Neoaustrarana; Streicher et al. 2018) is sister to the remaining Hyloidea (Cornucopirana), and
611 that Telmatobiidae is sister to other members of Cornucopirana (Streicher et al. 2018). The
612 remaining hyloids generally belong to the groups Amazorana and Commutabirana (Streicher et
613 al. 2018). Commutabirana also includes Terraranae. However, the tree of Jetz and Pyron (2018)
614 is broadly discordant with our trees and others within Hyloidea.

615 There is also disagreement between analyses within some of these groups. Within
616 Neoaustrarana (Fig. 2), the UCE-only data show strong support for the relationships: (Alsodidae,
617 (Batrachylidae, (Cycloramphidae, Hylodidae)). The gigamatrix tree (Fig. 3C) shows:
618 ((Cycloramphidae, Hylodidae), (Alsodidae, Batrachylidae)). Hime et al. (2021) found the
619 relationships: (Cycloramphidae, (Hylodidae, (Alsodidae, Batrachylidae))). The concatenated
620 likelihood analysis of Feng et al. (2017) did not support the monophyly of Neoaustrarana,
621 because their concatenated analysis placed Cycloramphidae in Commutabirana. Jetz and Pyron
622 (2018) did support monophyly of Neoaustrarana, and the relationships: (Cycloramphidae,
623 (Batrachylidae, (Alsodidae, Hylodidae))).

624 Within the predominantly South American clade Amazorana (Figs. 2, 3C), our UCE-only
625 and gigamatrix trees support the relationships: (Hylidae, (Hemiphractidae, Ceratophryidae)).
626 Feng et al. (2017) placed Ceratophryidae as sister to the other two families, whereas Hime et al.
627 (2021) placed Hemiphractidae as sister to Hylidae and Ceratophryidae. Jetz and Pyron (2018) did
628 not place these three families together.

629 Relationships were more congruent within Commutabirana. Our UCE-only and
630 gigamatrix (combined UCE-supermatrix) data (Figs. 2, 3D) support the relationships:

631 (Dendrobatidae, (Terraranae, ((Leptodactylidae, (Allophrynidae, Centrolenidae), (Bufonidae,
632 Odontophrynidae))))). Hime et al. (2021) found the same relationships, but they did not include
633 Allophrynidae. Feng et al. (2017) supported Dendrobatidae and Terraranae as successive sister
634 taxa to other members of this group (as did we), but other relationships were somewhat different,
635 and they included Cycloramphidae in this group as well. Jetz and Pyron (2018) did not support
636 monophyly of Commutabirana, but they did support a clade including: ((Bufonidae,
637 Odontophrynidae), (Leptodactylidae (Allophrynidae, Centrolenidae))). This is congruent with
638 our results.

639 Finally, there was general agreement among these studies on higher-level relationships
640 within Terraranae. The UCE data alone (Fig. 2) supported the relationships: (Brachycephalidae
641 (Eleutherodactylidae (Craugastoridae, Strabomantidae))). The gigamatrix dataset (Fig. 3D) and
642 those of Feng et al. (2017) and Hime et al. (2021) supported similar relationships, but with
643 Ceuthomantidae included as sister to all other terraranans. However, the tree of Jetz and Pyron
644 (2018) differed in placing Eleutherodactylidae and Brachycephalidae as sister taxa.

645

646 **Divergence Times**

647 The best smoothing value for the treePL analysis of the full gigamatrix tree was 1, based on the
648 cross-validation analysis. We also conducted an analysis with the 29 rogue taxa excluded (where
649 the best smoothing value was 1,000). Note that both smoothing values were intermediate (neither
650 the smallest nor largest examined), suggesting that the optimal value was indeed within the range
651 examined. The trees are shown in Supplementary Files S11 and S12 (all taxa vs. no rogues) and
652 are available in newick format in Supplementary Files S18 and S19.

653 Compared to previous studies (Tables S4, S5), our divergence times were similar for
654 shallow nodes in the phylogeny, but were often younger for deeper nodes. In particular, the
655 origin of Leiopelmatoidea (Ascaphidae [North America] + Leiopelmatidae [New Zealand]) was
656 estimated to be substantially younger (106 Mya, for all taxa) than previous studies (Feng et al.
657 2017; Jetz and Pyron 2018; Hime et al. 2021). Nevertheless, a Middle Cretaceous origin of
658 Leiopelmatoidea is plausible and a hypothesis with some precedent. Both geological evidence
659 and estimates from other vertebrate timetrees (e.g., moas from New Zealand and their American
660 relatives, ~80 Mya) suggest that continental connections between New Zealand and the Americas
661 were present in the Late Cretaceous (Cooper et al. 2001; Kula et al. 2007). Indeed, some

662 amphibian biologists have previously used this time frame to calibrate the minimum divergence
663 time of Leiopelmatoidea to the Late Cretaceous (Roelants and Bossuyt 2005).

664

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814 Figure S1. Swarm plots of alignment characteristics for different marker classes. Comparisons
815 are shown for alignment length, percent informative sites, and percent missing data. Data are
816 also summarized in Table 3.

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819 Figure S2. Phylogenetic estimate of anurans based on the species-tree analysis of 3,784 UCE loci
 820 using ASTRAL-III. The analysis is based on gene trees generated from untrimmed MAFFT
 821 alignments. Scale bar represents coalescent units. Asterisks indicate families that are inferred to
 822 be polyphyletic in this tree. Local posterior probabilities for each node are given in
 823 Supplementary File S5, Fig. S2.

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826 Figure S3. Maximum likelihood tree from the unpartitioned gigamatrix analysis. Scale bar
 827 represents substitutions per site. The phylogenetic tree is shown across four panels (A–D), with
 828 letters on branches representing connection points across panels. Bootstrap values for each node
 829 are given in Supplementary File S5, Fig. S4.
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(B)

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841 Figure S4. Estimated tree from maximum likelihood analysis of the supermatrix. The
 842 supermatrix consists of the 307 AHE, NPCL, and legacy markers (no UCes included). Scale bar
 843 represents substitutions per site. The phylogenetic tree is shown across four panels (A–D), with
 844 letters on branches representing connection points across panels. Bootstrap values for each node
 845 are given in Supplementary File S5, Fig. S7.

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863 Figure S5. Tree from concatenated maximum likelihood analysis of the gigamatrix, with rogue
 864 taxa removed. Scale bar represents substitutions per site. The phylogenetic tree is shown across
 865 four panels (A–D), with letters on branches representing connection points across panels.
 866 Bootstrap values for each node are given in Supplementary File S5, Fig. S7.
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886 Table S1. Voucher information for tissue samples used this study.

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Species	Museum number/ Collector ID	Family	Subfamily
<i>Aglyptodactylus madagascariensis</i>	UF 153651	Mantellidae	Laliostominae
<i>Amnirana lepus</i>	GBC-A 0344	Ranidae	-
<i>Anaxyrus americanus</i>	JJW 729	Bufoidea	-
<i>Arthroleptis poecilonotus</i>	UF 180748	Arthroleptidae	-
<i>Ascaphus montanus</i>	DSM 0840	Ascaphidae	-
<i>Boophis jaegeri</i>	UF 153611	Mantellidae	Boophinae
<i>Brachytarsophrys feae</i>	CAS 224375	Megophryidae	Megophryinae
<i>Breviceps macrops</i>	CAS 193965	Brevicipitidae	-
<i>Buergeria oxycephalus</i>	MVZ 230427	Rhacophoridae	Buergeriinae
<i>Callulina krefftii</i>	CAS 168715	Brevicipitidae	-
<i>Clinotarsus alticola</i>	CAS 232169	Ranidae	-
<i>Conraua crassipes</i>	CAS 258318	Conrauidae	-
<i>Cophyla occultans</i>	UF 153629	Microhylidae	Cophylinae
<i>Cornufer pelewensis</i>	CAS 236907	Ceratobatrachidae	Ceratobatrachinae
<i>Duttaphrynus stomaticus</i>	ID 7602	Bufoidea	-
<i>Dyscophus guineti</i>	MVZ 238743	Microhylidae	Dyscophinae
<i>Gastrotheca griswoldi</i>	MTD-TD 833	Hemiphractidae	-
<i>Guibemantis liber</i>	MVZ 238740	Mantellidae	Mantellinae
<i>Hemisus perreti</i>	UF 180509	Hemisotidae	-
<i>Hoplobatrachus rugulosus</i>	CAS 240996	Dicroglossidae	Dicroglossinae
<i>Hymenochirus boettgeri</i>	CAS 253587	Pipidae	-
<i>Hyperolius pardalis</i>	UF 180880	Hyperoliidae	-
<i>Indirana leithii</i>	ID 7600	Ranixalidae	-
<i>Kalophrynus pleurostigma</i>	CAS 245749	Microhylidae	Kalophryninae
<i>Kaloula pulchra</i>	CAS 210158	Microhylidae	Microhylinae
<i>Kassina maculosa</i>	UF 180614	Hyperoliidae	-
<i>Leptobrachium smithi</i>	CAS 247976	Megophryidae	Leptobrachiinae
<i>Leptopelis aubryi</i>	CAS 258070	Arthroleptidae	-
<i>Leptopelis calcaratus</i>	UF 180849	Arthroleptidae	-
<i>Microhyla berdmorei</i>	CAS 213432	Microhylidae	Microhylinae
<i>Occidozyga martensii</i>	CAS 239421	Dicroglossidae	Occidozyginae
<i>Odontobatrachus natator</i>	CAS 230055	Odontobatrachidae	-
<i>Pelobates cultripes</i>	MVZ 231951	Pelobatidae	-
<i>Pelodytes ibericus</i>	MVZ 186009	Pelodytidae	-
<i>Petropedetes vulpiae</i>	GBC-A 0526	Petropedetidae	-
<i>Phrynobatrachus auritus</i>	UF 180893	Phrynobatrachidae	-

<i>Phrynomantis annectens</i>	CAS 255056	Microhylidae	Phrynomerinae
<i>Phyllomedusa duellmani</i>	KU 212206	Hylidae	Phyllomedusinae
<i>Pipa pipa</i>	MVZ 247509	Pipidae	-
<i>Ptychadena aequiplicata</i>	UF 180901	Ptychadenidae	-
<i>Rana pipiens</i>	JJW 748	Ranidae	-
<i>Rhinophrynus dorsalis</i>	MVZ 137712	Rhinophrynidae	-
<i>Rhombophryne testudo</i>	UF 153589	Microhylidae	Cophylinae
<i>Scaphiophryne marmorata</i>	MCZ A-136273	Microhylidae	Scaphiophryninae
<i>Scaphiopus couchii</i>	DMP 1742	Scaphiopodidae	-
<i>Tomopterna tuberculosa</i>	JET 0033	Pyxicephalidae	Cacosterninae
<i>Trachycephalus jordani</i>	KU 217771	Hylidae	Hylinae
<i>Trichobatrachus robustus</i>	UF 180821	Arthroleptidae	-
<i>Zhangixalus nigropunctatus</i>	CAS 242203	Rhacophoridae	Rhacophorinae

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Abbreviations are as follows: CAS: California Academy of Sciences; DSM: Daniel S. Moen field series; DMP: Daniel M. Portik field series; GBC, Gabon Biodiversity Collection; ID: Indraneil Das field series; JET: James Titus-McQuillan field series; JJW: John J. Wiens field series; KU: Biodiversity Institute and Natural History Museum, University of Kansas; MCZ: Museum of Comparative Zoology, Harvard University; MVZ: Museum of Vertebrate Zoology, UC Berkeley; UF: Florida Museum of Natural History, University of Florida.

896 Table S2. List of rogue taxa identified by RogueNaRok.
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Genus	Family
<i>Anomaloglossus</i>	Dendrobatidae
<i>Aphantophryne</i>	Microhylidae
<i>Barbarophryne</i>	Bufoidea
<i>Bijurana</i>	Randae
<i>Bryophryne</i>	Craugastoridae
<i>Chimerella</i>	Centrolenidae
<i>Duttaphrynus</i>	Bufoidea
<i>Frostius</i>	Bufoidea
<i>Ghatophryne</i>	Bufoidea
<i>Gracixalus</i>	Rhacophoridae
<i>Hoplophryne</i>	Microhylidae
<i>Indosylvirana</i>	Ranidae
<i>Itapotihyla</i>	Hylidae
<i>Lankanectes</i>	Nyctibatrachidae
<i>Leptomantis</i>	Rhacophoridae
<i>Liuixalus</i>	Rhacophoridae
<i>Melanobatrachus</i>	Microhylidae
<i>Micrixalus</i>	Micrixalidae
<i>Minyobates</i>	Dendrobatidae
<i>Niceforonia</i>	Craugastoridae
<i>Oreophrynella</i>	Bufoidea
<i>Paedophryne</i>	Microhylidae
<i>Phyloria</i>	Myobatrachidae
<i>Pseudobufo</i>	Bufoidea
<i>Pseudopaludicola</i>	Leptodactylidae
<i>Sigalegalephrynus</i>	Bufoidea
<i>Strabomantis</i>	Strabomantidae
<i>Tachiramantis</i>	Strabomantidae
<i>Vandijkophrynus</i>	Bufoidea

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Table S3. Comparison of congruence and support among higher-level nodes in the gigamatrix, UCE, and supermatrix trees. For each clade in the partitioned gigamatrix ML tree, we give the bootstrap support values (Giga-BS). We also give the bootstrap values for the higher-level clades in the UCE-only concatenated ML tree (UCE-BS) and in the supermatrix tree (Super-BS). For the UCE tree, if the relevant taxa in a clade were not present in the UCE tree, this is noted under “UCE clade.” We also note here if a conflicting clade was supported instead, and the bootstrap value for that clade is given under UCE-BS. Similarly, under “Supermatrix clade” we report if a different clade was supported, and the bootstrap value for that clade is given under Super-BS (note that the listing of supermatrix clades that are in conflict with the gigamatrix tree do not align perfectly with clades in the gigamatrix tree). If nothing is listed under UCE clade and/or under Supermatrix clade, then that clade in the gigamatrix tree is supported in one or more of those trees. Bootstrap values of clades that are incongruent with the gigamatrix tree are also indicated in red.

Higher-level clade in gigamatrix tree	Giga-BS	UCE-BS	UCE clade	Super-BS	Supermatrix clade
Frog monophyly	100	100		100	
Leiopelmatoidea	100		no <i>Leiopelma</i>	100	
Frogs above Leiopelmatoidea	100	100		94	
Discoglossoidea	100	100		100	
Frogs above Discoglossoidea	100	100		92	
Pipoidea	100	100		100	
Frogs above Pipoidea	100	100		94	
Pelobatoidea	100	100		100	
Pelodytidae+Pelobatidae+Megophryidae	100	100		95	
Pelobatidae+Megophryidae	100	100		100	
Neobatrachia	100	100		100	
Frogs above Heleophrynidae	100		no Heleophrynidae	93	
Ranoidea+Sooglossidae+Nasikabatrachidae	100		no Sooglossidae, Nasikabatrachidae	69	
Sooglossidae+Nasikabatrachidae	100		no Sooglossidae, Nasikabatrachidae	100	
Ranoidea	100	100		100	
Afrobatrachia+Natatanura	100	100		37	
Afrobatrachia	100	100		100	
Hemisotidae+Brevipectidae	100	100		100	
Arthroleptidae+Hyperoliidae	100	100		100	

Natatanura	100	100		100	
Natatanura above Micrixalidae	33		no Micrixalidae	7	Natatanura above Phrynobatrachidae+Ptychadenidae
Natatanura above Pyxicephalidae	31	100		23	Conrauidae+Odontobatrachidae+Petropedetidae+Pyxicephalidae
Conrauidae+Petropedetidae	97	100		22	Odontobatrachidae+Petropedetidae+Pyxicephalidae
Natatanura above Conrauidae+Petropedetidae	28	89	Conrauidae+Petropedetidae+Odontobatrachidae+Phrynobatrachidae+Ptychadenidae	32	Odontobatrachidae+Petropedetidae
Odontobatrachidae+Phrynobatrachidae+Ptychadenidae	97	100		4	Natatanura above Phrynobatrachidae+Ptychadenidae+Conrauidae+Odontobatrachidae+Petropedetidae+Pyxicephalidae
Phrynobatrachidae+Ptychadenidae	99	100		11	
Natatanura above Odontobat+Phryno+Ptychadenidae	38	100		4	Micrixalidae+Nyctibatrachidae+Ceratobatrachidae
Ranixalidae+Nyctibatrachidae+Ceratobatrachidae	36	100	no Nyctibatrachidae	17	Micrixalidae+Nyctibatrachidae
Nyctibatrachidae+Ranixalidae	18		no Nyctibatrachidae	13	Dicroglossidae+Ranixalidae+Ranidae+Mantellidae+Rhacophoridae
Natatanura above Ranixalidae+Nyctibatrachidae+Ceratobatrachidae	97	100		14	Dicroglossidae+Ranixalidae
Ranidae+Mantellidae+Rhacophoridae	98	100		61	
Mantellidae+Rhacophoridae	100	100		90	
Hyloidea + Myobatrachidae+Calyptocephalellidae	100	100		100	
Myobatrachidae+Calyptocephalellidae	100	100	Calyptocephalellidae+Hyloidea	100	
Hyloidea	100	100		100	
Hyloidea above Rhinodermatidae	99	100		97	Hyloidea above Dendrobatidae

Neoaustrarana	87	100		87	Hemiphractidae+Terrarana
Cycloramphidae+Hylodidae	100	100		43	
Alsodidae+Batrachylidae	87	100	Batrachylidae+Cycloramphidae+Hylodidae	61	
Hyloidea above Neoaustrarana	100	100		99	Hyloidea above Dendrobatidae, Hemiphractidae+Terrarana
Hyloidea above Telmatobiidae	87	100		40	Hyloidea above Hylidae
Amazorana	100	100		76	Odontophrynidae+ Ceratophryidae+ Rhinodermatidae+ Cycloramphidae+Hylodidae+Telmatobiidae+Alsodidae+Batrachylidae
Ceratophryidae+Hemiphractidae	83	78		28	Ceratophryidae+Rhinodermatidae+ Cycloramphidae+Hylodidae+Telmatobiidae+Alsodidae+Batrachylidae
Commutibarana	87	100		30	Rhinodermatidae+ Cycloramphidae+Hylodidae+Telmatobiidae+Alsodidae+Batrachylidae
Commutibarana above Dendrobatidae	87	99		25	Cycloramphidae+Hylodidae+Telmatobiidae+Alsodidae+Batrachylidae
Terrarana	100	100		100	
Terrarana above Ceuthomantidae	100		no Ceuthomantidae	97	
Eleutherodactylidae+Strabomantidae+Craugastoridae	74	100		61	Brachycephalidae+Strabomantidae+ Craugastoridae
Strabomantidae+Craugastoridae	89	100		38	
Commutibarana above Terrarana	87	100		41	Telmatobiidae+Alsodidae+Batrachylidae
Leptodactylidae+Allophrynidae+Centrolenide	66	100		36	
Allophrynidae+Centrolenide	100	100		100	
Odontophrynidae+Bufonidae	87	100		23	Bufonidae+Leptodactylidae+Centrolenidae+Allophrynidae
Mean bootstrap	88.52	99.26		67.06	

Table S4. Comparison of estimated clade ages in this study (gigamatrix tree, all taxa included) to a selection other recent trees. Ages are approximate for most clades, since many studies did not provide labeled, time-calibrated trees. The newick tree is available as Supplementary File S18.

Clade	This study	Feng et al. (2017)	Hime et al. (2021)	Jetz and Pyron (2018)
Crown Anura	178	210	210	222
Crown Leiopelmatoidea	107	195	200	160
Crown Alytoidea	125	140	140	168
Crown Pipoidea	148	160	160	168
Crown Pelobatoidea	135	125	120	151
Crown Neobatrachia	136	140	140	178
Crown Hyloidea	82	70	70	157
Crown Ranoidea	103	100	105	143

Table S5. Comparison of estimated clade ages in this study (gigamatrix tree, rogue taxa excluded) to a selection other recent trees. Ages are approximate for most clades, since many studies did not provide labeled, time-calibrated trees. The newick tree is available as Supplementary File S19.

Clade	This study	Feng et al. (2017)	Hime et al. (2021)	Jetz and Pyron (2018)
Crown Anura	177	210	210	222
Crown Leiopelmatoidea	100	195	200	160
Crown Alytoidea	125	140	140	168
Crown Pipoidea	148	160	160	168
Crown Pelobatoidea	135	125	120	151
Crown Neobatrachia	138	140	140	178
Crown Hyloidea	87	70	70	157
Crown Ranoidea	106	100	105	143

